

Hydrochemical Toxicants and Their Pathophysiological Nexus with Renal Dysfunction: A Mechanistic Insight

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ABSTRACT

A crucial and indispensable part of our biological system is ground water. Groundwater is frequently used in industry and for irrigation. Both natural and man-made causes of contamination can affect ground water. Ground water pollutants have enormous effect on human health. The various health effects that cause due to major ground water pollutants include gastrointestinal disorders, methamoglobinemia, dental fluorosis and suffer from acute and chronic toxicities of liver, kidneys, circulatory system and Nervous system. Among various organs kidneys are one of the most susceptible organs to toxicity due to these water pollutants. Occuring of high levels of fluoride, arsenic, cadmium, chromium, nitrates and other toxic substances in ground water leads to various renal abnormalities including decreased Glomerular filtration rate, tubular renal damage, proteinuria, glycosuria, phosphaturia, progressive renal damage. In this review we underlined the impact of various major ground water pollutants in development of renal diseases.

Keywords: Ground water pollutants, Kidneys, Glomerular filtration rate, Renal damage.

INTRODUCTION

Water is a vital natural resource utilized for drinking and other developmental functions in our daily life ¹. Safe drinking water is the need for human health all over the world. Being Universal solvent water is a major source of infection. As per WHO, 80% diseases are water borne ².

Surface water and Ground water are both important sources for water supply. Till today for many rural and urban families, ground water serves as a decentralised source of drinking water.. Further ground water is extensively used for irrigation and industrial purposes. There is growing concern on the deterioration of ground water and there by its impact on human health. Ground water can become contaminated by natural sources or various types of human activities. Municipal, residential, commercial,

industrial and agricultural activities all affect ground water quality ³.

Ground water looks normally clear and clean as the ground naturally filters out the particulate matter. But there are various natural and human induced organic and inorganic impurities found in ground water. As ground water flows through the ground heavy metals like iron, manganese, cadmium, arsenic, chromium gets dissolved and may later found to be in high concentrations in the water. Industrial discharges, urban activities, agriculture, ground water pumpage, leakage of septic tanks, leaking fuel tanks, disposal of wastes and toxic pills affect ground water by increasing the levels of nitrates, microbes and other toxic contaminants ⁴. The source and the effect of major ground water chemical pollutants is mentioned in Table 1.

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Table 1: Sources and effects of major ground water chemical contaminants

Pollutant	Source	Effects on health
Arsenic	Occurs naturally and from industrial wastage	Liver and hepatic damage, Carcinogen and decreases haemoglobin
Fluoride	Occurs naturally	Crippling bone disorder, Kidney damage and stain teeth
Lead	Industry wastage and mining	Harmful effects growth of children, carcinogen, liver and kidney damage
Cadmium	Industrial discharge and mining waste	Leads to high blood pressure, liver and kidney damage and anemia.
Chromium	Mining, fossil fuel combustion and waste incineration	Cause liver and kidney damage, ulcers and dermatitis
Nickel	Naturally in soils	Damages heart and liver
Nitrates and nitrites	Fertilizers, feed lots and sewage	Methamoglobinemia
Sulfates	Mineral dissolution, salt water intrusion, domestic or industrial waste	At high doses have laxative effect
Thallium	Pharmaceutical manufacturing and other industrial waste	Harmful effect on kidneys, liver and intestine
Pesticides	Agricultural wastes	Damages nervous system, thyroid, reproductive system, liver and kidneys

Raise in overall salinity and presence of high concentrations of fluoride, arsenic, cadmium, chromium, nitrates and other toxic substances in ground water has undergone a change to an extent that its use is hazardous. Ground water pollutants have enormous effect on human health. Drinking ground water can expose people to harmful pollutants apart from pathogens. The various health effects that cause due to major ground water pollutants include gastrointestinal disorders, methamoglobinemia, dental fluorosis and suffer from acute and chronic toxicities of liver, kidneys, circulatory system and Nervous system⁵. Among various organs kidneys are one of the most susceptible organs to toxicity due to these water pollutants. Hence in this chapter we would focus on the impact of major ground water pollutants in development of renal diseases.

KIDNEYS:

Kidneys are paired organs found on each side of the back portion of the abdominal cavity. The larger left kidney is located a bit higher than the right kidney. Unlike other organs found in the abdomen, the kidneys are located behind the lining of the abdomen cavity, thus they are considered retroperitoneal organs. These bean shaped organs are protected by the

back muscles and the ribs, as well as the fat that surrounds them like a protective padding⁶.

Nephron is the functional unit of kidney. The nephron consists of a glomerulus, proximal convoluted tubule, loop of Henle, distal tubule and collecting duct. The glomerulus comprises a tuft of capillaries projecting into a dilated end of the renal tubule. Most nephrons lie largely or entirely in the cortex. The remaining 12%, called the Juxtamedullary nephrons, have their glomeruli and convoluted tubules are located at the junction of the medulla and cortex⁷.

Kidneys are one of the main sources for removal of extra/harmful metabolites from the body. Almost all the waste products such as urea, which is the waste product of protein metabolism, creatinine (from muscle creatinine), uric acid, bilirubin products, metabolites of various hormones and drugs etc are eliminated by kidneys through urine which a medium for the excretion of these substances. Being exposed to wide variety of metabolites kidneys are highly susceptible for toxicity of harmful agents.

Renal Dysfunction/ failure:

Renal dysfunction/failure is decrease in renal function that including abnormal retention of serum creatinine

and blood urea. And it can be characterized by decrease in Glomerular filtration rate, Inability of kidney to excrete metabolites and Failure in regulation of electrolyte balance. Depending on severity it is of two type namely acute renal failure and chronic renal failure

CHEMICAL POLLUTANTS IN GROUND WATER AND THEIR EFFECTS ON KIDNEY:

Arsenic: Arsenic is one of the most common heavy metals in nature. It is a wide spread environmental pollutant and millions of population suffers from exposure to this metal. Contamination of drinking water with arsenic found to be linked in the development of renal damage. Arsenic is absorbed through intestine, lungs and skin and widely distributed in the body. It gets methylated in the liver in a GSH-mediated metabolic process which decreases its toxicity and helps in biliary and urinary excretion. It enters intracellular medium through aquaglyceroporins AQ3 and AQ9. Researchers reported that increase in cellular expression of these aquaglyceroporins increases intracellular accumulation of arsenic. MRP-1 and 2 (Multi drug resistance protein) are also another group of arsenic transporting proteins which transport arsenic bound to GSH to bile. The MRP-2 transporter is also present in proximal tubule cells which favour accumulation of arsenic in these cells. Further arsenic is filtered through glomeruli and reabsorbed in proximal tubules. Mainly arsenic toxicity in proximal convoluted tubular cells is because of GSH depletion and oxidative activity of free radicals ⁸.

Till today there are no complete evidences in literature on all the clinical manifestations of arsenic toxicity in kidneys. But the limited information available suggests that exposure to arsenic leads to the decreased Glomerular filtration rate, tubular renal damage, proteinuria, glycosuria, phosphaturia, progressive renal damage. In many cross sectional studies carried throughout the world a positive correlation between urinary arsenic and chronic kidney diseases (CKD) was reported and there was four fold increased risk of CKD. Arsenic induced acute renal failures are also evidenced tubulointerstitial nephritis and acute tubular necrosis

manifested by albimunuria, nephrocalcinosis, hypercalciuria and necrosis of the renal papillae ⁹.

Fluorides: Fluorine is the 13th most abundant chemical element on earth and is present naturally in its anionic form fluoride. It is present mainly in igneous and sedimentary rocks and enters ground water through water-rock interactions. In some areas fluoride content in ground water is as high as 15% based on the geochemistry of the surrounding area. There is a direct link between fluoride and development of renal diseases.

Excess amount of fluorides is toxic to mammalian kidneys and the most vulnerable is the tubular areas of the kidney. Fluorides exhibit renal accumulation mainly in the cortical and juxtaglomerular areas where the proximal tubules are located. Fluorides in excess amounts disrupt the collagen synthesis in the body and leads to kidney damage apart from damage to other organs. Further fluoride inhibits some kidney and other enzyme pathways leading to dysfunction of kidneys ¹⁰.

Different mechanisms are reported in fluoride induced nephrotoxicity include oxidative stress, inflammation, autophagy, genotoxicity and apoptosis. Researchers evidenced that abnormal cell apoptosis is the key link to fluoride induced renal damage ¹¹. In many scientific investigations, cells exposed to fluoride showed many types of ultrastructural changes including swollen mitochondria, vacuole formation and apoptosis because of fluoride induced generation of reactive oxygen species and oxidative stress ^{12,13}. A number of case reports suggested that mainly chronic exposure of fluorides leads to the development of chronic kidney diseases. Further various case reports evidenced the fluoride induced nephrotoxicity by studying various markers like BCL2, Nacetyl- β -d-glucosaminidase, caspase-3 and caspase-9 ^{14,15}.

Lead: The toxic effects of lead are known since the times of Roman. Compared with past present exposure to high concentrations of lead intake was less due to better industrial management. Even though lead contamination is still a public health problem in many countries in Africa, Asia and Latin America because of domestic exposure via contaminated soil and water. Increasing evidences of literature reported that lead can be considered as a high risk factor in

developing cardiovascular morbidity and kidney dysfunction^{16,17}.

The major route of absorption for lead is intestine and respiratory system. The lead binds to the proteins and distributes to the soft tissues and bones. Bones being the main reservoir of lead increases the transport of lead into the blood stream during high burn turn over like adolescence and pregnancy. Finally urinary excretion is the major route of elimination of lead from the¹⁸. Based on results in many cases people exposed to lead reported for faster attenuation in renal function and higher mortality rates. Further researchers in their study evidenced that people exposed to lead over long period found to be in the risk of chronic renal failure¹⁹.

Many underlying mechanisms are reported for the development of renal toxicity due to exposure for lead. Lead bounds to low molecular weight proteins and filtered through glomerulus and reabsorbed by Proximal convoluted tubular cells. Inside the cell, lead causes mitochondrial damage, formation of free radicals and apoptosis. Further lead induces activation of intra renal renin angiotensin system and generates inflammatory responses in renal interstitium which will be involved in progression of tubule interstitial damage and high blood pressure²⁰.

In researches it has been illustrated that increased production of free radicals by lead declines Nitric oxide production and enzyme guanylate cyclase expression. High blood pressure also accompanied with the lead exposure stimulates the activation of NADPH oxidase which effects oxidative stress and intracellular redox potential [21]. Furthermore studies showed that lead can interact with calcium binding proteins, which inhibits calcium uptake by mitochondria. It acts as a substrate for calcium transporters entering the mitochondria of tubular cells and thereby declines the oxidative metabolism in the kidney²².

Cadmium: Cadmium is an important industrial agent and environmental pollutant that is an important cause of various health complications. Based on its dose and duration of exposure it leads to the toxicity of various organs like lungs, liver, bones and kidneys. Cadmium is reported as a prominent nephrotoxin and low levels of cadmium exposure also leads to the development

of renal abnormalities. Based on different epidomological studies carried in various countries it was proved that cadmium is a direct nephrotoxin and exposure to it causes the development of kidney diseases^{23,24}.

Cadmium bounds to proteins, mainly metallothionein and phytochelatin which are broken down by gastric juice releasing cadmium. Thus released cadmium will be absorbed in intestine by transporters namely DMT-1 and ZIP-8. In circulatory blood it gets transported to liver where it binds to Glutathione and metallothenein-1. This complex gets secreted in bile and reabsorbed into blood by enterohepatic circulation. This Cadmium-Metallothenein complex easily filtered by glomerulus and absorbs into S1 segment of proximal tubule. In Proximal tubular cells the accumulation of cadmium results in mitochondrial dysfunction, formation of free radicals, apoptosis and reabsorptive dysfunction²⁵. Further the studies on long term exposure to cadmium revealed that cadmium exposure leads to decline in glomerular filtration rate, proteinuria and developed of CKD²⁶. The study of prominent tubular damage biomarkers like KIM-1, NAG, alpha-1 and beta-2 microglobulin are used in early detection of cadmium induced renal injury and provided the basis for molecular mechanisms underneath the cadmium induced proximal tubular injury²⁷.

Chromium: Chromium, being a micronutrient naturally present can lead to life threatening diseases when ingested in high levels. Contamination of ground water with chromium occurs mainly due to chemical industries, leather tanning and alloy manufacturing industries etc. Major factors associated with toxicity of chromium compounds are oxidation state and solubility. The hexavalent Chromium (VI) type are powerful oxidizing agents and tend to be more toxic compared to Chromium trivalent (III) type (poor absorption). The hexavalent chromium absorbed by lungs and GIT and later enters into the blood stream and gets distributed to the cells. The accumulation of chromium in tubular cells in the process of elimination may leads to the renal damage²⁸.

In the literature, the results showed that in people exposed to chromium there are the evidences of

glomerular and tubular injury^{29,30}. Researchers reported that low doses of chromium also lead to the proximal tubular injury and damage to brush border membrane may be the reason under the chromium nephropathy. In epidemiological studies it was found that elevated urinary β_2 microglobulin levels have been found in chrome platers which were an indicator of renal toxicity. The molecular mechanism of chromium induced nephrotoxicity is still unclear. In rodents it was reported that chromium accumulates predominantly in renal cortex and leads to renal necrosis. DNA damage and oxidative stress was reported in animal kidneys on exposure to chromium³¹. Still further research on chromium induced nephrotoxicity is needed to understand the molecular mechanisms underneath the renal damage in humans exposed to chromium.

Nitrites and Nitrates: Nitrates in high concentration in ground water may mainly occur from naturally decomposed organic matter, septic waste and leaching of fertilizers. Nitrates and nitrites on high concentrations (more than 1000mg/ml in adults) leads to metabolic acidosis and which further contributes to kidney failure. Still there are many uncertainties and lack of epidemiological studies on the area on the renal impairments upon long term ingestion of nitrites and nitrates³².

Thallium: Thallium is a non-essential and highly toxic metal listed by USEPA. Thallium levels in water occur by natural and anthropogenic sources. In general it is present in low levels but human activities like industrial waste, coal burning and mineral smelters raises the levels of Thallium. Thallium even in low concentration is highly toxic. It is absorbed through all routes, widely distributed and largely eliminated³³. It causes cellular damage and intracellular mitochondrial injury. In human case studies it is reported that renal function is impaired in thallium exposed patients and upon histological studies of rat kidneys it was found that there was severe necrosis in renal cortex³⁴.

Pesticides: Pesticides are chemicals composed of not only oxygen, sulfur, chlorine, nitrogen and phosphorus as well as heavy metals such as arsenic, lead etc. Improper use of pesticides results in water pollution. Pesticides when sprayed on crops they flow

below the surface of ground and reach water bearing aquifers making it contaminated and toxic on ingestion. In many researches undergone worldwide chronic kidney diseases are reported in many areas with indiscriminate use of artificial fertilizers. It was stated that the presence of heavy metals in these pesticides is one of the most prominent reason for the development of nephropathy in people consuming ground water³⁵.

CONCLUSION

Ground water contamination is a global issue and many people are facing worst results of consuming contaminated water. As the chemical contaminants are the major reason of ground water pollution measures are necessary to raise awareness and recruit into action the policies to control the major sources of contamination by establishing proper disposal of industrial wastes, alternatives to chemical fertilizers and pesticides etc. Education and awareness programmes are also to be conducted to raise the knowledge among the people about the health complications on direct consumption of contaminated ground water. Being renal injury as one of the major health complication due to this contamination there is a dire need to develop experimental designs and demonstrate the relationships between chemical contaminants and renal dysfunction. Further wide research is required to study the cellular and molecular mechanisms involved in the renal injury caused by the specific contaminants and their impact on the health of the society.

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